

Leadership Performance Optimization: Effects on Team Achievement in Organizational Sustained Success

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Abstract

This paper aims to explore the nature and the function of leadership performance in organizations. Researchers address and assess how leadership can progress to be of maximum use of employees' capabilities and to view teams as performing organizational units which is similar to other studies that focus on teamwork processes.

Survey data from 72 teams (n = 279) was collected in three industrial institutions in the private sector) in the United Arab Emirates. The results are leaders develop or modify plans of action to address priorities to improve the employees' performance, allocate needed resources and communicate plans to organization. Directing and controlling team appeared strongly related with the team employees towards their organization. Effective management network between team members' was positively associated with the followers' performance and negatively with innovative commitment. In addition, understanding organizational goals appeared strongly related to Team's Leadership.

Keywords: Leadership, Team Leadership, Confidence, Performance, UAE

Introduction

Performance may be defined as the continuous process of identifying, measuring, developing the performance of individuals and teams, and the aligning performance with the strategic goals of the organization (Guinis, 2013). Performance management is not performance appraisal.

Management performance optimization is not just the workforce "working harder". It is the result of maximized productivity from several factors ranging from leadership behavior, employees, technology and process, culture, and motivation and reward systems. Continually, the majority of the organizations monitor performance indicators to assess the actual performance based on its scope of service. The management compiles the data and submits the report concerning the quality leadership team for review (Zubin, & Venkat, 2011). Therefore, if an indicator does not meet the expected level of performance, the management has to submit a plan of action to be implemented to improve the required performance.

The overall goal of organizational performance is to ensure that the management, including its processes, departments, teams, and employees, are working together effectively and efficiently in an optimum fashion to achieve the results desired by the organization (Wang, Law, Hackett, Wang, & Chen, 2005).

The organizations' management serves on appointed teams and has their departmental peer review activities which may identify solutions that are referred to the organization's problems or operational issues for resolution. Hence, leadership team reviews reports

monitoring organization wide performance, such as customers' satisfaction, clients' complaints, or variance reporting.

In any organization employees, managers, and leaders represent the best source of sustainable competitive advantage and performance in today's global marketplace. Organizations that leverage these variables are better positioned to address the challenges of change, competition, and uncertainty, and to experience higher levels of productivity and quality of performance. For example, leading changes, improving employees' customer and business focus, and enhancing corporate reputation and brand may create a strategy and program from the inside out to help the organization's clients (Rousseau, 2006).

To achieve acceptable organizational performance and to enhance organization's competitiveness in the marketplace it is crucial for management through the leaders to provide the services that will give their organizations the most value from planning to implementation. For Abhishek, Kathryn, & Edwin, (2006), strategic change to employee engagement in the decision making process, leadership alignment to employer branding, and internal research to communications function assessments, altogether offer a wealth of accomplishments that focus on the strong correlation between business performance and an organization's ability to effectively engage and communicate with the internal and external stakeholders (Gang, Stephen, & Amy, 2011). Despite the concepts of performance management regarded as an ongoing process, there is an increasing demand in business to

institutionalize these practices in the organization. Such convergence is due to the increased demand for accountability on the part of governing bodies, the public in general, the media, and commitment of managers deliberately to strengthen performance.

Employees, managers, and leaders are the best source of sustainable competitive advantage and performance in organization and today's global marketplace. Therefore, directing employees as a team, which is formed to realize problems' solutions cannot be realized by individuals and differs completely from managing individuals. These include different conceptions of leadership, cope with constraints, exchange of information and developing individual skills. In fact the organizational performance improvement efforts by the management and through leaders is regarded as away of performance improvement process that provides the organizational infrastructure to systematically assess, plan, manage and evaluate achievements. In fact an organization's performance goals can only be achieved through its employees (Natalia, Matthew, & Henry, 2013).

The organizational performance improvement process benefits various levels of the organization by providing the opportunity for employees throughout the organization to be involved in performance improvement. But balancing business and principles is not always easy, for example, challenging decisions can require compromises and the ethical dilemmas where it is hard to the leader to weigh up the consequences of a decision already taken (Patrick, Roseanne, & Neil, 2009). Also to develops or modifies a plan of action to address priorities to improve performance, allocates needed resources and communicates plans within the organization structure, otherwise the organization has to evaluate the outcomes and effectiveness of plan of action. It's important for leaders to hang on to personal values because one of the most difficult things as a leader is the management of ambiguity in business contexts. Yet they need to do this alongside having clear network of communications (Bono, & Judge, 2003). Leaders have got to lead and they've got to resist any undesirable changes. Therefore, networking is an essential skill for leaders to have when working with teams. In this meaning connectivity is creating mutually beneficial relationships between the leader and his team. Both, the leadership and teamwork to plan, measure and analyze, and manage performance.

The researchers' belief is that when the majority of the employees within the organization share values consistently then there's a strong culture and that is definitely going to have an impact on the employees' productivity and outcomes, the individuals'

performance, as well as the organizational achievement of goals.

Effective leadership is likely to be even more essential in the future to facilitate the growth and adaptation of human services organizations in the constant challenge to improve performance, therefore employees' development is focused on the development of core competencies, attitudes and behaviors that are fundamental to leading, managing and performing in the context of performance-leading organization (Frank, & Heike, 2009).

Leadership Performance may be regarded as a systematic and an oriented approach to management and leadership to achieve high performing organizations through teamwork and individuals. Such understanding is fundamental to leading, managing and performing organizational attitudes and goals through the teamwork core of competencies, attitudes and behaviors (Hilde, Gro, & Tom, 2008). Such approach exploits the fact that by clarifying and then satisfying the needs of key stakeholders of the organization then organizational performance may be improved.

This paper indicates that successful knowledge leadership retention is significantly related with higher reported organizational performance.

Teamwork Engagement and Improvement for Performance

For a leader to achieve organizational goals, it is essential for each individual in the team to understand his specific roles and responsibilities for goal achievement, and there must be continuous dialogue between leaders and the teamwork to set performance expectations, monitor progress, and evaluate results (Guihyun, Matthias, & Richard, 2013).

An effective performance management in the organization system links the leader and the teamwork behaviors to the organization's business strategies, goals, and values (Steffen, & Christopher, 2013). The leader should ensure any action steps that are interlinked and ongoing in an organizational culture that successfully maintain and account for the required performance.

In business organizational change and organizational learning will be necessary to regularly improve customer services and organizational effectiveness. Therefore, Leaders also need to ensure alignment among organizational processes, including strategy, culture, management systems, programs, and required resources (Packard, 2004). Such understanding consolidates the contributions of management and leadership capabilities within the organization, and then builds on improving customers' perceptions and expectations. This

systematic sustainability of improvements may be achieved in terms of knowledge sharing, innovation and continuous learning. In fact such understandings are fundamental tools and techniques leading to the organizational performance or their business effectiveness (Hernez-Broome, & Hughes, 2004).

To reach an acceptable performance to their organizations' expectations leaders require a definable destination, an inspiring connection between the desired futures and a more distant yet treasured past, and a sense of innovating, to bridge the performance gap and raise the bar to achieve performance leadership (Hoffman, & Jones, 2005). These organizations depend on leaders developing their outcomes orientation, and focusing efforts on the priorities to deliver valuable results and outcomes. Such organizations have a deep faith in and faithfulness to their employees and the people they serve (Mary, 2005).

These organizations invest in leadership that raise and rally the performance of the organization by lifting up its members morally, emotionally and spiritually, through a combination and progression of leadership styles and strategies.

These organizations pay prudent attention to sustainable growth rates and the use of the applied indicators and targets in order to assess its progress and performance from the available resources used. On the other hand leaders on their part in such organizations have a strong sense of direction for their organization, which they continually share and communicate (Judge, & Piccolo, 2004).

The message and the constant understanding between those leaders and their organization is the quality of work. The existence of sustainable growth is an evident in the leadership successions that characterize many of the organizations now a day (Eagly, & Carli, 2003). In this respect the team knows exactly what it has to accomplish and is motivated by high degrees of internal collaboration.

Leaders should build powerful teams to produce much better results through developing their cultural and relationship skills, as an attempt to develop robust productive relationships. They are generating loyalty through the demonstration of their ability to work hard and long to achieve what is wanted and to engage others in the quest. Thus they actively build relationships and engender strong trust among colleagues in order to take high risks as they know their team members well (Yoo, & Brooks, 2005). In fact, leaders keep people together through active trust among a team whose members work effectively together. Those leaders have an absolute determination to succeed whatever the odds. Their individual influence is in their ability to mobilize energy among the team members.

Such leaders have a profound belief in their ability to perform at the highest level and achieve their demanding targets. They are resolute in their determination to succeed and set high expectations for themselves and those who work with them.

In the design and development of an organization to achieve a positive performance, the management or the leadership team should annually assess the organization's logistical needs. This has resulted in the creation of a variety of activities modules designed to meet the business needs (Tucker, & Russell, 2004). This logistics focuses on developing a visual reference to verify product quality and usability. Operational procedures, service standards and in-process control measures for all core processes, each product, and support services are carefully designed and documented in the organization's operations procedures.

Leadership usually requires the fusion of many kinds of management initiatives, for example, inspiring, courageous, distributed and sustainable among others. In fact, it is leadership that pushes teamwork forward, raises them up and brings them together in pursuit of a common and inspiring purpose that is greater than any one of them. For effective work performance, leaders' management system links the employees and teamwork behaviors to the organization's business strategies, goals, and values (McNeece, & Thyer, 2004). Therefore, it is essential for each employee to understand individual roles and responsibilities for goal achievement, and there must be continuous dialogue between leaders and employees to set performance expectations, monitor progress, and evaluate results. Together, leadership and staff work to plan, measure and analyze, and manage performance (Krishnan, 2005). Output and outcome of performance can be analyzed to determine whether resources need to be increased, shifted, or altered in some way to meet goals and achieve desired results.

Performance indicators provide an understanding of the relationship between outputs and outcomes, thereby enhancing the ability of the teamwork leaders to increase resource investment in preferred outcomes (Wong, & Law, 2002). Moreover, performance achievement and targets should be discussed and processed within a valued and respectful relationship of personal consideration, knowledge and even inspiration between leaders and the employees within the teamwork – even when the targets are imposed. Therefore performing beyond expectations may mean knowing individuals' capabilities, but not without encouraging the teamwork individuals' initiatives.

The management should restructure the organization on the socialist principle of sharing responsibility for the future of the organization with the employees and to continue to operate on this philosophy. Such concept

may be regarded as an integration of qualities within the employees over time and in an attempt to narrowing achievement gaps (Leban, & Zulauf, 2004).

The conclusion is that management needs to expand beyond just performativity and help contribute to social and political change. Therefore, performance takes place and can be measured at the organizational, process, and individual levels. Consistent with Blau (2003), of integrated model of teamwork, we distinguish between different conceptions of leadership, Cope with constraints, Exchange of information, and developing individual skills (Figure 1).

Figure (1) is about here

Evaluating Leadership Teamwork Effectiveness

Leadership values help performance in the long term. It has consequences for reputation and trust in business, and a huge impact through employee engagement, productivity and outcomes. In this meaning leaders and under the pressures of targets may find themselves in a positions to behave unethically and still get good business results in the short term, but it's likely to come back and leave such attitude later.

One of the main problems for business leaders is subjectivity, when there are no clear cut rules on ethics and, the meaning of ethics changes from one person to another. With an increased focus on corporate responsibility, many organizations have made efforts to embrace an ethical culture among employees (Alice, & Wilco, 2013). Therefore, values may provide a useful framework, and the ethics of an organization are ultimately set by its leaders.

Leaders' performances are the way of managing and leading the organization for success. This is achieved through focusing continuously on creating stakeholders' value of the organizational faster with more cost effectiveness, developing the work environment conditions throughout the organization, shared sense of collaboration, vision and purpose developing commitment of the employees, clarifying strategic priorities, and leaders' skills and efficiency using best practice techniques to make the organization more efficient and effective (Romero, 2005). Performance is an abstract concept and must be represented by concrete, measurable phenomena or events to be measured.

Then the task of the teamwork leaders is to develop their strategic capabilities, and above all more effectively translate strategies into ongoing operations within their organizations, in an attempt to develop their outcomes orientation, to focus efforts on the priorities to deliver valuable results and outcomes and a fight or struggle against a formidable and resisting challenge.

H 1: High levels performance of team's leader will be positively related to the employees' performance commitment.

Organizations' replacement of leadership, or may be staff at all levels within the entire organizations is a common turnaround preference within business. Thus, a change of managers can produce quick and temporary lifts as motivation is revived, teams' individuals or employees try to impress their new boss, and those who were out of favor have the opportunity of a fresh start, these effects only last for a while before performance sinks again (Roberts-DeGennaro, & Packard, 2002). Therefore Management should concentrate on long-term improvement as well as making the immediate changes that build confidence and enable their organizations to survive.

The temptation of some organizations' management to change everyone and everything may be one reason why most turnaround efforts in businesses fail. In fact organizations should be characterized by well-managed leadership succession and high leadership stability. The challenge is to find the right leaders for the right problems at the right time and to stick with the choice when it begins to show evidence of success.

Given the ambiguity of ethics, personal principles may not be shared by every one of the team members, and problems happen when people are not authentic. So for leader, valuing principles must be about honesty and having an open conversation. Ethics are not just important for the sake of the organizations, but also for the leaders themselves. When a leader didn't have a reference to his values then they are likely to end up with stress and uneasy task to take on a different persona. Thus, trust and confidence is very important for employees, teams, and leaders (Venkat, & Pooja, 2008).

The primary goals of organizational improvement are to increase organizational effectiveness and efficiency to improve the ability of the organization to deliver goods and/ or services. A third area sometimes targeted for improvement is organizational efficacy, which involves the process of setting organizational goals and objectives.

The researchers' believe that through a focus on teamwork engagement and environment, the management will experience a significant positive and measurable performance, but lacking insight into workplace belief systems, values, motivations, and disincentives will underlie the behaviors targeted for change. Leaders should be aware about how to stimulate fundamental, sustainable change in the way and their organization does its business. Therefore, leadership

strive to provide skills, knowledge, a principle-based mindset, and work habits required for producing excellence and practicing life-long learning.

H 2: High levels performance of team's leader will be positively related to the team employees' towards their organization.

For Rene, Frans, & Vasi (2008), managers were urged to promote teamwork through reward systems and new organization forms, to pay for performance, to train managers and staff at all levels in total quality principles, to deploy cross-functional teams to re-engineer core business processes, and to employ the available strategies while downsizing, outsourcing, simplifying, and producing just-in-time results. No organization could employ these strategies without employees' cooperation and an effective leadership. However, the individual management had sufficient evidence about the relative effectiveness of various improvement programs to take effective decision about where best to invest limited time (Henrik, & Mary, 2013). The goal is to add value. In response, leaders should utilize a number of techniques and programs to support the workforce including learning and training development opportunities that are not strictly focused on job responsibilities.

H 3: High levels of performance of team's leader will be positively related to employees' understanding organizational goals.

They also strive to prepare their employees, not only for their job within their organization, but beyond, by extending their contributions to their communities believing which is a major responsibility to the local communities in shaping the employees or the team works individuals into positive citizens. By helping the employee grow, develop, and become more skillful, leader helps the business become more successful while also making the communities a better place to live and work (Greg, 2006).

Innovation is the key to improving health and sustaining the organization's growth and profitability. The quest for innovative solutions should invigorate all of the core businesses and pervade the organization's community in general. In the drive to innovate, the management supports well-conceived risk-taking and understands that it will not always lead to success. In this respect, management embraces creativity and consistently pursues new opportunities, ways to make its products and services more useful to the customers, the business

practices more efficient and effective. In general, performance takes place and can be evaluated at the organizational, process, and individual levels, through the evaluation of the effectiveness and outcomes of common indicators of workforce engagement and satisfaction, for example in increased retention, promotion and training opportunities.

The Research Model and Methodology

Our conceptual model illustrated in Figure (1), consists of two parts. The first part addresses the nature of the managing teamwork concept. In this model managing teamwork is presented as a latent variable, composed of different conception of leadership, cope with constraints, exchange of information, and developing individual skills. The second part of the model examines the relationship between team's leadership and several teamwork effectiveness variables such as understanding organizational goals, communication and trust, followers' performance, and innovative commitment.

Sample

A survey study conducted in three industrial institutions in two provinces in the Abu Dhabi District in the United Arab Emirates. These organizations are from the private sector. They perform functional services, and commercial and market oriented. Initially 80 teams (380 individuals) were asked to participate in this study. A total of 279 individuals divided into 72 teams provided data via a questionnaire. The participation rate was 90.0 per cent. The three industrial institutions in this study will be mentioned as 1, 2, and 3. The size of the teams ranged from three to five. The sample included 30 teams from institutions 1, 22 from institutions 2, and 20 from institution 3. (Table1).

Table (1) is about here

Measures

All variables in our model were measured with validated instruments. The scale consisted of self-report items scaled in a five-point Likert scale (1= completely disagree to 5= completely agree). The reliability of the scale is satisfactory showing Chronbach Alphas > 0.57. See (Table 2).

Table (2) is about here

Teams Leadership:

This was measured with four scales (Costa, 2000), seven items measuring being a team player (e.g. "Employees should always tell the truth even if they know that lying is better"), eight items measuring participation propensity (e.g. "Some employees have accomplished their success by stepping on other employees"), eight items measuring cooperative behaviors (e.g. "Employees exchange up-to-date information with each

other"), and three items measuring leadership skills (e.g. "Employees keep checking if other employees maintain their promises and pledges").

Understanding Organizational goals:

This was measured with nine- item scale from the Expanded Delft Measurement Kit from Roe et al. (1997). An example is " Our team deserves a good assessment from our boss").

Communication and Trust:

This was measured with a five- item scale from Smith and Barclay (1997) that assesses the extent to which team members are satisfied with their teamwork. One item of this scale is " We are content with what other employees contribute to our group".

Followers Performance & Innovative Commitment

These were measured with five-scale item developed by Freese and Schalk (1996). An example of a value commitment item is " My personal norms and principles keep up a correspondence with the organization priorities", and of performance commitment item is " Some new plans forced me to leave this organization".

Research Analysis

The team's levels agreement was examined using ANOVA method, and within-group integrated agreement index-rwg. (Zhu and Dowling, 2002). Values of rwg equal to 0.59 or above demonstrate high consistency within groups and justify the aggregation within that team. In our study the results of ANOVA techniques indicate that the calculated F-ratios are greater than the tabulated F which gives significant results. This is the same result provided by Cristena study (2003), as an acceptable level for internal consistency. The minimum evidence for differences across teams is provided by an F-ratio >1.00 (Hays, 1991).

To examine the structural properties of the teamwork components and the dependent variables we run two confirmatory factor analyses. (Table 3). The measurement model for the teamwork components distinguished between being a team player (six items), participation propensity (six items), cooperative behaviors (six items) and leadership skills (three items). The comparative- fit index CFI = 0.85 indicates a good model fit, although the four- factor model shows a significant χ^2 . Both the goodness of-fit index GFI, and the adjusted goodness of fit-index AGFI are moderate, and the parsimonious goodness of fit indices PGFI and PNFI indicate a good parsimonious fit. The models with

four and three factors show adequate fit according to this ratio, $\chi^2/df = 1.33$, and 1.86 respectively, whereas only the four-factor model obtained a comparative fit > 0.85. Therefore, we favored the four-factor model for teamwork above the other concurrent models. For the dependent variables the measurement model distinguished between understanding organizational goals and commitment & trust, followers' performance, and innovative commitment. This structure fitted the data reasonably well. The adequacy of concurrent models with one, two and three factors was examined. The chi-square is significant the ratio χ^2/df is < 2.0. (Table 3). The results show that χ^2 is highly significant; therefore we consider the four-factor model as an adequate structure for the dependent variable.

Table (3) is about here

Table (4) is about here

Hypotheses Testing

To test the research hypotheses, we used structural equation modeling. The adequacy of the models used was examined using several indices to fit. The chi-square, with no-significant values showing a good model fit. The ratio χ^2/df , with values below 1.9 suggesting a good model fit (Erez, and Judge, 2001). The comparative-fit index (CFI) (Sheldon and Kasser, 2001), the goodness of-fit index (GFI), and the adjusted goodness of fit-index (AGFI), these indices indicate a good model fit for values > 0.85. The parsimonious fit was assessed with the parsimonious goodness of fit-index (PGFI) and the parsimonious formed fit-index (PNFI). Values > 0.50 indicate a good parsimony fit. The analysis of the residuals was made using the root-mean error of approximation (RMSEA) and the root mean squared-residual (RMR). For this research values of RMSEA < 0.02 indicate a good fit. In general and for RMR values > 0.06 indicate a poor fit, and < 0.05 indicate a good fit.

Based on the four-factor structure obtained from the measurement model for the teamwork components we created a model for teamwork using four observed variables. These variables were obtained by summing the item scores in each factor into a total score. In table (4) the results indicate that this model fits the data well: $\chi^2 1.89(df = 2, p = 0.22)$, GFI is 0.94 and the AGFI is 0.91. The CFI is 0.94 and the RMSEA and RMR are both < 0.03. In this model, reducing conflict is the strongest component of teamwork ($\gamma = 0.66$) and explains 75 percent of the total variance of teamwork. Sharing information explain 51 per cent of the total variance of teamwork and are the second strongest component of teamwork ($\gamma = 0.44$). With $\gamma = 0.06$, accepting leadership structure explains 7 percent of the variance of teamwork. Leadership skills, relates

positively with teamwork ($\gamma = 0.23$). All these structural relations were statistically significant (t -values > 1.79). The conceptual model was tested with five latent variables, teamwork, understanding organizational goals, communication and trust, followers' performance, and innovative commitment. The results for this model indicate a marginal fit to the data in table (3).

The χ^2 is significant $\chi^2 = 131.21$ ($df = 99$, $p = 0.01$), the other fit indices show values lower than 0.80, and the residual fit indices values above > 0.05 , which is compatible with the poor fit of this model. The modification indices suggested a path from perceived goal specification to communication and trust to improve the fit. The modification model shows a considerable improvement of fit as shown in table (4). In particular, the χ^2 becomes non significant and the residual coefficient RMSEA decreases to 0.03, which indicates a good model fit. The other indices show also improvement and GFI reaches 0.83, showing almost an adequate fit. Based on these results we considered the modified model more adequate to fit out data. The results of the structural equations are displayed in Figure 2.

Figure (2) is about here

Team leadership is positively related with understanding organizational goals ($\gamma = 0.16$), and communication and trust ($\gamma = 0.14$), both confirming the H1, and H2. The strongest relations are for followers performance ($\gamma = 0.35$) and for innovative commitment ($\gamma = 0.26$) confirming H3. The new information age requires that any firm's employees should learn to work effectively in teams, working in most effective environments for employees to develop their skills, and creating environment where they aren't afraid to participate. Although our components cannot be directly compared with those found in other studies, reducing conflict were the strongest components of teamwork. This is consistent with the dominant way of thinking in the literature about value and share-the opportunities team members have to engage in dialogs that involve different viewpoints, options, and even culture.

Sharing information were the second strongest component of teamwork, which supports in particular the incorporation of behaviors in models of teamwork. Accepting leadership structure explained also the third strongest percentage of the total variance of teamwork. However, we consider that both components still should be viewed as important aspects of managing teamwork.

Conclusion

Effective leadership is likely to be even more essential in the future to facilitate the growth and adaptation of

human services organizations in the constant challenge to improve performance.

All components appeared positively related with the managing teamwork effectiveness. Research shows that a key factor limiting organizational success is a systemic failure to provide effective development for employees and teams in the fundamental skills of management and leadership and, leadership performance is the way of managing and leading the organization for success. In relation to understanding organizational goals the research findings support the main effect between managing teamwork and performance. The relationship between Teamwork and communication and trust in this study is positive, however, cope with constraints was strongly related to understanding organizational goals.

The organization must view performance improvement as a process that requires a clear plan to improve performance and address resource requirements to enable this process to be successful. Teams' leadership was particularly strongly associated with the followers' performance and performance commitment in the organization. When teams' leadership quality is low, levels of followers' performance and commitment tend to decrease, while effective leader commitment tends to arise, and such implications can bring additional problem, for instance in contexts of change when additional levels of efforts and involvement are needed to successfully implement these changes. This process requires a change in the working culture and full commitment from the top of the organization to the lowest levels to execute this plan for improving performance.

Limitations of the study

The term 'team's leadership' has become important in recent years, and has many conditions. The foremost limitation is the number of teams in the study sample ($n = 279$). Therefore, our conclusions should be carefully interpreted. Another limitation refers to the fact the teams in this study came from organizations within the private sector only, which makes it inappropriate to generalize these conclusions to other sectors of economy science. Cautions in the interpretation of these results are also associated with the use of self-ratings of teams' leadership.

One variable that may have influenced the results in this study, is the risk associated with poor performance of leadership. Therefore researchers should address such variable in order to provide better interpretations of the results.

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Figure (1): The Research Model

Different conceptions of leadership Skills	Cope with constraints	Exchange of information
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Table (1): Respondent of Team Details

Details of Sample	Total No. of Team	No. of Individuals In Each Team			Details of Respondents
		3	4	5	
Institution 1	30	10	10	10	28 * 3 = 84
Institution 2	22	9	8	5	25 * 4 = 100
Institution 3	20	9	7	4	19 * 5 = 95
Total	72	28	25	19	279

Instead

Table (2) Main Characteristics of the Scale

Variable	M	SD	α	F ratio	rwg
Being a Team Leader	26.01	5.73	0.67	1.82	0.65
Participation Propensity	22.50	4.95	0.70	1.89	0.64
Cooperative Behavior	29.71	5.80	0.65	1.83	0.62
Leadership Skills	10.30	2.09	0.55	1.85	0.59
Intelligence & Skills	20.34	3.44	0.57	1.87	0.61
Reduce Conflict	13.51	2.01	0.68	1.91	0.65
Care Values	16.45	2.30	0.56	1.82	0.63
Merit Performance	9.26	2.55	0.66	1.80	0.62

Note:

α : is Chronbach alpha.

M: is mean scale

F: is ratio ANOVA.

rwg: is the within-group interrater agreement.

Table (3): Fit indices for the measurement models

The Models	χ^2	df	p	χ^2/df	GFI	AGFI	CFI	PGFI	PNFI
Teamwork Cohesiveness									
Four factors	180.10	135	0.01	1.33	0.45	0.41	0.85	0.53	0.52
Three factors	230.91	137	0.00	1.86	0.40	0.35	0.72	0.50	0.50
Two factors	235.65	135	0.00	1.74	0.29	0.21	0.59	0.40	0.40
One factors	240.66	138	0.00	1.73	0.20	0.12	0.49	0.38	0.31
Team Effectiveness									
Four factors	39.10	33	0.01	1.18	0.69	0.60	0.68	0.43	0.45
Three factors	59.62	35	0.00	1.70	0.61	0.51	0.51	0.42	0.37
Two factors	65.89	37	0.00	1.78	0.60	0.50	0.41	0.40	0.30
One factors	66.87	39	0.00	1.72	0.51	0.41	0.21	0.45	0.21

Notes:

Independent model for teamwork cohesiveness $\chi^2 = 1.069.21(p = 0.001)$.

Independent model for teamwork effectiveness $\chi^2 = 372.38(p = 0.00)$.

Table (4): Fit indices for the structural models.

Structural models	γ	Error	R^2	χ^2	GFI	AGFI	RMSEA	RMR	CFI	PGFI	PNFI
Teamwork				1.89(df=2; p=0.22)	0.94	0.91	0.01	0.08	0.94	0.53	0.53
Accepting leadership structure	0.06	0.71	0.9								
Sharing information	0.44	0.20	0.61								
Cooperative behavior	0.66	0.49	0.31								
Leadership skills	0.23	0.79	0.02								
Conceptual model				130.21 (df = 99; p = 0.01)	0.75	0.70	0.03	0.06	0.72	0.55	0.55
Modified model				113.06(df = 98; p = 0.05)	0.83	0.75	0.02	0.05	0.78	0.55	0.48
Individual skills	0.06	0.61									
Reduce conflict	0.86	0.58									
Core values	0.20	0.68									
Merit & performance	0.52	0.31									
Teamwork → Individual skills	0.16										
Teamwork → Communication & trust	0.14										
Teamwork → Followers Performance	0.35										
Teamwork → Innovative commitment	0.26										
Reduce conflict intelligence & → skills	0.46										

Figure (2): The Structural relations:

